

Synthesis And Evaluation Of Antinociceptive Activity Of Seven Membered Dibenzodiazepine-1,7-Dione Derivatives Via Annulation

Pratiksha Tayade, Sachin Dighade

Department Of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Institute Of Pharmacy And Research Badnera, Amravati, Maharashtra, India.

ABSTRACT

The present study focuses on the synthesis of novel seven-membered dibenzodiazepine 1,7-dione derivatives via annulation and evaluation of their antinociceptive activity using the hot plate method. Six derivatives (PT I – PT VI) were synthesized and characterized by UV, FTIR, Mass, and NMR spectroscopy. The synthesized compounds were evaluated for analgesic activity using Diclofenac as standard drug. Results demonstrated significant increase in reaction time compared to control, indicating promising central analgesic activity. Among synthesized derivatives, PT IV and PT VI exhibited superior antinociceptive potential. The study suggests that dibenzodiazepine-1,7-dione scaffold may serve as a potential lead for development of novel analgesic agents.

Keywords: Dibenzodiazepine, Annulation, Antinociceptive activity, Hot plate method, Diclofenac.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 PAIN SENSATION:

Physiologically, pain occurs when sensory nerve endings called nociceptors (also referred to as pain receptors) come into contact with a painful or noxious stimulus. The resulting nerve impulse travels from the sensory nerve ending to the spinal cord, where the impulse is rapidly shunted to the brain via nerve tracts in the spinal cord and brainstem. The brain processes the pain sensation and quickly responds with a motor response in an attempt to cease the action causing the pain.[1] **1.2 BASIC MECHANISMS OF PAIN:**

Fundamentally, the basic pain mechanism undergoes three events—transduction, transmission and modulation when there is a presence of noxious stimuli. For instance, transduction occurs along the nociceptive pathway following such order:

(1) stimulus events are converted to chemical tissue events;

(2) chemical tissue and synaptic cleft events are then changed into electrical events in the neurons;

(3) electrical events in the neurons are transduced as chemical events at the synapses

1.3 SEVEN MEMBERED RING:

New synthetic methods continue to be developed to construct seven-membered heterocyclic rings containing one, two, or three of the heteroatoms N, O, or S. The focus of much of the literature has been on ring systems containing at least 1 N atom, which has often been driven by a desire to prepare these heterocycles in a stereo-controlled fashion, the search for new bioactive compounds, and the synthesis of natural products. Prominent synthetic methods include transition metal- and photoredox-catalyzed, cycloaddition/annulation, cascade, and C-H functionalization processes. In a 7-membered ring, the heteroatom must be able to provide an empty π -orbital (e.g. boron) for "normal" aromatic stabilization to be available; otherwise, homoaromatic may be possible. [2,3] Seven-membered rings are relatively small and therefore have a significantly reduced

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entropy when compared to polymers and macrocycles, which are prepared from the same components.

Annulation, derived from the Latin word *annulus* (ringed) means "the formation of rings". In organic chemistry this term is used to describe the process of building a ring onto a pre-existing system, cyclic or non-cyclic. This broad definition includes in a general sense many reactions that are not thought of as annulation reactions, such as Diels-Alder reactions, acid catalyzed polyolefin cyclizations, photochemical, radical and thermal cyclizations. A transformation involving fusion of a new ring to a molecule via two new bonds. Some authors use the term "annelation" for the fusion of an additional ring to an already existing one, and "annulation" for the formation of a ring from one or several acyclic precursors.

1.4 DIBENZODIAZEPINE-1,7-DIONE:

The preparation of natural products and drugs is one of the most significant fields in organic synthesis, as well as the rapid construction of molecular complexity naturally existing in these bioactive compounds. The benzodiazepine ring system is found in a range of compounds that exhibit a wide variety of pharmacological behavior. Dibenzodiazepinedione derivatives, an important subfamily of benzodiazepines, have proved to be valuable in the area of CNS agents and are also being used as serotonin and dopamine modulators. Furthermore, according to structural analysis of naturally occurring products, dibenzodiazepine ring-containing compounds are found in many other biologically active compounds, specifically marine cyclic peptides and alkaloids. Since their total synthesis has been a significant challenge for organic chemists for many years, the development of new synthetic routes should be of great interest.[4]

However, the backbone of the dibenzodiazepinedione unit is inherently rigid, possessing a seven-membered ring. To date, the majority of reported syntheses of dibenzodiazepinediones generally involve the condensation of hydrazines and orthoesters, involving various cyclization steps that require additional functionalities. To achieve a more concise route direct from readily available precursors, quite a few

methods constructing the seven-membered dibenzodiazepinedione ring system have been reported, but most processes required a large excess of hydrazine aldehyde precursors of the dibenzodiazepinediones or were conducted with low reaction efficiency. One-pot multicomponent annulation reactions avoiding the use of a large excess of formaldehyde or hydrazine precursor are still very significant in synthetic organic chemistry. Recently, the C–H activation/C–C formation cascade process has provided valuable access to diverse functionalities in a single step, and the versatile methodologies are emerging as an attractive tool.

1.5 ANTINOCICEPTIVE ACTIVITY:

Antinociceptive activity refers to the ability of substances to inhibit the sensation of pain. This effect is crucial in developing analgesics and involves various mechanisms, including interaction with opioid receptors and modulation of neurotransmitter systems.

The use of traditional and herbal medicine, especially for the treatment of various diseases and infections, is as ancient as human society. Pain is a disagreeable sensory and emotional experience and is a significant health care problem being treated primarily by using pain management medicines globally. Several drugs, both natural and synthetic, are available in the market for the treatment of pain. Despite being effective for the treatment of pain, synthetic drugs can show side effects and tolerance development. Over the years, a variety of medicinal plants and several plant-based pure natural compounds have proved to be effective in the management of different degrees of pain. Various experimental models are used to identify the anti-nociceptive activity of extracts and compounds using laboratory animals. [5,6,7]

The simplest and fastest evaluation of the antinociceptive action occurs through the hot-plate test, where animals are placed on a surface previously heated to a constant temperature, causing an escape reaction. Many preclinical studies aim to identify groups of molecules with promising antinociceptive activity in hot-plate test.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1 MATERIALS:

INSTRUMENT:

Sr. no.	Name of instrument	Name of Company
1.	Microprocessor Melting / Boiling Point Apparatus	Systonic lab and scientific instrument, near industrial estate Panchkula, Panchkula, Haryana, INDIA.
2.	Digital analytical weighing balance	CAS-234, Contech instrument limited near Punit industrial premises, Turbhe, Navi Mumbai Maharashtra, INDIA
3.	Hot air oven	Labhosp instrument and equipment Mfg., Goregaon east, Mumbai
4.	UV Spectrophotometer	Shimadzu UV -1800 series
5.	Magnetic stirrer	Labhosp instrument and equipment Mfg., Goregaon east, Mumbai
6.	FTIR	Shimadzu, sharp analyticals, Nagpur
7.	Analgesiometer (Eddy's hot plate)	Techo electronics Lalbagh, Lucknow 226001(U.P.) INDIA

CHEMICALS:

Sr. no.	Name of chemical	Name of company
1.	Ethyl Benzoate (C ₆ H ₅ COOCH ₂ CH ₃)	Pallav chemicals and solvents Pvt. Ltd. Boisar, INDIA.
2.	Hydrazine Hydrate (N ₂ H ₄ ·H ₂ O)	Avra synthesis Pvt. Ltd. Hyderabad, Mumbai.
3.	Ethanol	Alsucrose Corporation, Pune, Maharashtra, INDIA
4.	Ethyl acetoacetate (C ₆ H ₅ COCH ₂ COOCH ₂ CH ₃)	Pallav chemicals and solvents Pvt. Ltd. Boisar, INDIA.
5.	Sodium hydroxide (NaOH)	Avra synthesis Pvt. Ltd. Hyderabad, Mumbai.
6.	Iodobenzene Acetoacetate (C ₆ H ₅ I-COCH ₂ COOEt)	Pallav chemicals and solvents Pvt. Ltd. Boisar, INDIA.
7.	Benzoyl chloride	Pallav chemicals and solvents Pvt. Ltd. Boisar, INDIA.
8.	Chloroform	Pallav chemicals and solvents Pvt. Ltd. Boisar, INDIA.
9.	Hexane	Avra synthesis Pvt. Ltd. Hyderabad, Mumbai.

2.2 METHODS

2.2.1 Hot Plate Method: This test measures thermal pain sensitivity. Mice are placed on a heated surface (typically around 55°C), and the latency time until

they exhibit a pain response (like paw licking or jumping) is recorded. The response time is assessed at multiple intervals post-treatment to determine analgesic effects. A cutoff time of 30 seconds is set to prevent injury. [6,7]

The pre-reaction time to the thermal stimulus was recorded as the time interval from introduction of the animals to the plate maintained at 55 ± 0.5 °C until the first lick of the hind or fore paw or the first jump of the animals. The animals were initially screened and those that responded to heat stimulus within the cut-off time were randomly batched for study. Each group was administered via intra peritoneal, the test agents as follows: group I (vehicle), group II (standard), group 3 (test compound), group 4 (PT I to PT VI). The time necessary for rat that licked their fore and hind paw was measured at interval of 30 min post-oral administration. Baseline was calculated with the use of measurement obtained at 60 and 30 min before the administration of the compound, vehicles, standard, as a normal reaction of the animal to the temperature. The calculation of the area under the curve (AUC) of response from 30 min after drug administration until the end of the experiments was used to indicate the antinociception.

The subsequent reactions of the animals were recorded at 30 minutes intervals for 120 minutes following the administration of all treatments [8].

Principle: In this method heat is used as a source of pain. Animal are individually placed on a hotplate maintained at constant temperature and the reaction of

animal such as hind paw licking or jumping response is taken as the end point.

Animals: Adult male vistar rat (100-200 gm) were used throughout this study. The animal were randomly housed in appropriate cages at 22°C on a 12 hrs light/ dark cycle with free access to food and water, 60 - 80 % humidity. Before each test, the animal were acclimatized to the laboratory for at least 1 h. The animal were procured from animal house of Institute Of Pharmaceutical Education And Research Borgoan (Meghe), Wardha. Rats were used in group of six animals in each group.

Procedure: Rat weighing 100 – 200 gm were used. Rat were placed on hot plate, which consists of electrically heated surfaces. Temperature of the hot plate was maintained at 55°C. response such as hind paw licking or jumping, withdrawal of the paw are seen and recorded. The time period (latency period), when the rat was placed and until response occurred was recorded by a stopwatch. The vehicle, standard, test were administered intraperitoneally, and latency period was recorded after 30,60,90 and 120 min for each group. The time rat spent licking the hind paw was recorded and this was considered as the nociceptive reaction.[9]

Figure No. 1: The techno digital heated plate Analgesiometer (or Eddy's Hot Plate)

3.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

3.1 RESULTS:

Table no. 01: Reaction time for test 1 treatment. (PT I)

Sr. no.	Treatment	Reaction time			
		15 min	30 min	60 min	120 min
1.		10 sec	10 sec	13 sec	12 sec

2.	Test 1 (PT I)	11 sec	12 sec	15 sec	11 sec
3.		10 sec	11 sec	11 sec	13 sec
4.		11 sec	12 sec	10 sec	15 sec
5.		9sec	10 sec	13 sec	14 sec
6.		8sec	13 sec	14 sec	13 sec

Table no.02: Reaction time for test 2 treatment. (PT II)

Sr. no.	Treatment	Reaction time			
		15 min	30 min	60 min	120 min
1.	Test 1 (PT II)	9 sec	11 sec	13 sec	12 sec
2.		8 sec	13 sec	15 sec	13 sec
3.		11 sec	11 sec	15 sec	13 sec
4.		9 sec	12 sec	10 sec	11 sec
5.		13 sec	10 sec	13 sec	14 sec
6.		14sec	11 sec	14 sec	13 sec

Table no.03: Reaction time for test 3 treatment. (PT III)

Sr. no.	Treatment	Reaction time			
		15 min	30 min	60 min	120 min
1.	Test 1 (PT III)	13 sec	14 sec	14 sec	13 sec
2.		12 sec	11 sec	15 sec	15 sec
3.		13 sec	11 sec	12 sec	13 sec
4.		11 sec	12 sec	14 sec	15 sec
5.		14sec	13 sec	13 sec	14 sec
6.		11 sec	11 sec	14 sec	15 sec

Table no.04: Reaction time for test 4 treatment. (PT IV)

Sr. no.	Treatment	Reaction time			
		15 min	30 min	60 min	120 min
1.	Test 1 (PT IV)	11 sec	10 sec	10 sec	14 sec
2.		10 sec	11 sec	10 sec	9 sec
3.		9 sec	11 sec	12 sec	13 sec
4.		10 sec	12 sec	10 sec	10 sec
5.		11 sec	10 sec	11 sec	14 sec
6.		11 sec	9 sec	14 sec	11 sec

Table no.05: Reaction time for test 5 treatment. (PT V)

Sr. no.	Treatment	Reaction time			
		15 min	30 min	60 min	120 min
1.	Test 1 (PT V)	8 sec	9 sec	14 sec	15 sec
2.		10 sec	11 sec	15 sec	15 sec
3.		7 sec	11 sec	12 sec	13 sec
4.		6 sec	12 sec	10 sec	14 sec
5.		11 sec	10 sec	11 sec	14 sec
6.		14 sec	11 sec	14 sec	13 sec

Table no.06: Reaction time for test 6 treatment. (PT VI)

Sr. no.	Treatment	Reaction time			
		15 min	30 min	60 min	120 min
1.	Test 1 (PT VI)	11 sec	12 sec	15 sec	10 sec
2.		8 sec	11 sec	15 sec	9 sec
3.		10 sec	11 sec	12 sec	13 sec
4.		11 sec	12 sec	10 sec	12 sec
5.		10 sec	10 sec	11 sec	14 sec
6.		10 sec	10 sec	11 sec	12 sec

3.2 DISCUSSION:

In this study, a series of dibenzodiazepine-1,7-dione derivatives were synthesized via annulation reactions aimed potential antinociceptive activity. The design strategy was based on the structural framework of dibenzodiazepine, known for their potential interaction with central nervous system receptor particularly those implicated in pain modulation.

Synthesized derivatives:

In this present work the dibenzodiazepine-1,7-dione have been synthesized by reacting benzoyl hydrazide and diacetoxyiodobenzene via annulation reaction. The structure of synthesized compound was confirmed by UV, IR spectroscopy. The purity of compound was confirmed by TLC, melting point.

- Synthesis of (PT I) was confirmed by melting point, IR spectrum. Synthesized compound shown pale yellow solid (36.6 gm, 55%), melting point 160 - 161°C. ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆, 500MHz), δ 9.08(s, 1H), 1.08 (s,6H); 8.17 (d, J = 10.0 Hz, 1H), 7.36 (d, J = 10.0 Hz, 1H), 5.98 (s, 2H), 3.14 (s, 2H), 2.45 (s, 5H), 1.08 (s, 6H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR S-3 (DMSO-d₆, 125 MHz) δ 196.6, 160.4, 154.0, 143.3, 133.2, 128.0, 126.9, 124.9, 120.2, 107.4, 51.9, 40.1, 31.2, 27.9, 22.0; HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for C₁₆H₁₉N₂O₂⁺.
- The synthesis of (PT II) brown solid (54.4 mg, 95% yield). mp 196–197°C. ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆, 500 MHz) δ 8.84 (d, J = 2.5 Hz, 1H), 8.19 (d, J = 10.0 Hz, 1H), 7.14-7.12 (m, 1H), 5.96 (s, 2H), 3.87 (s, 3H), 3.14 (s, 2H), 2.45 (s, 2H), 1.08 (s, 6H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR (DMSO-d₆, 125 MHz) δ 196.7, 163.1, 160.1, 154.7, 135.1, 129.0, 116.1, 115.7,

107.0, 106.8, 55.4, 51.9, 40.2, 31.1, 27.9; HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for C₁₆H₁₉N₂O₃⁺.

- The synthesis of (PT III) brown crystal solid (52.5 mg, 79% yield). mp 173–175°C. ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆, 500 MHz) δ 9.58 (d, J = 1.5 Hz, 1H), 8.34 (d, J = 5.0 Hz, 1H), 7.82 (dd, J = 2.0, 8.5 Hz, 1H), 7.74-7.72 (m, 2H), 7.55-7.52 (m, 2H), 7.46-7.43 (m, 1H), 6.04 (s, 2H), 3.17 (s, 2H), 2.45 (s, 2H), 1.09 (s, 6H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR (DMSO-d₆, 125 MHz) δ 196.7, 160.4, 154.5, 144.6, 139.7, 133.5, 129.2, 128.4, 127.7, 127.2, 125.2, 123.2, 121.2, 107.5, 51.9, 40.1, 31.2, 27.9; HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for C₂₁H₂₁N₂O₂.
- The synthesis of (PT IV) white solid (48.1 mg, 83% yield). mp 157–159°C. ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆, 500 MHz) δ 9.29 (d, J = 5.0 Hz, 1H), 8.23 (d, J = 5.0 Hz, 1H), 7.54-7.52 (m, 1H), 6.02 (s, 2H), 3.15 (s, 2H), 2.45 (s, 2H), 1.07 (s, 6H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR (DMSO-d₆, 125 MHz) δ 196.5, 160.0, 155.4, 138.5, 134.1, 129.1, 126.7, 124.3, 120.8, 106.5, 51.6, 40.1, 31.2, 27.8; HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for C₁₅H₁₆ClN₂O₂.
- The synthesis of (PT V) white solid (57.4 mg, 86% yield). mp 175–177 °C. ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆, 500 MHz) δ 9.45 (d, J = 1.5 Hz, 1H), 8.14 (d, J = 10.0 Hz, 1H), 7.67-7.65 (m, 1H), 6.01 (s, 2H), 3.14 (s, 2H), 2.45 (s, 2H), 1.07 (s, 6H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR (DMSO-d₆, 125 MHz) δ 196.5, 160.1, 155.4, 134.3, 129.4, 129.1, 127.8, 127.4, 121.1, 106.4, 51.6, 40.1, 31.2, 27.8; HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for C₁₅H₁₆BrN₂O₂

The synthesis of (PT VI) Pale yellow solid (37.3 mg, 68% yield). mp 169–170°C. Eluents for column chromatography: petroleum ether/ethyl acetate (5:1

v/v). ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆, 500 MHz) δ 8.09-8.07 (m, 1H), 7.57-7.55 (m, 2H), 5.92 (s, 2H), 3.10 (s, 2H), 2.47 (s, 2H), 1.11 (s, 6H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR (DMSO-d₆, 125 MHz) δ 192.5, 159.9, 157.2 (d, 1J_{C-F} = 255.0 Hz), 152.6, 127.8 (d, 3J_{C-F} = 8.0 Hz), 125.5, 122.9, 120.9 (d, 2J_{C-F} = 15.0 Hz), 119.5 (d, 2J_{C-F} = 23.8 Hz), 108.3, 50.6, 39.6, 31.9, 28.2; HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for C₁₅H₁₆FN₂O₂.

4. CONCLUSION:

The current study successfully synthesized and evaluated novel dibenzodiazepine-1,7-dione derivatives, revealing promising antinociceptive activity by using hot plate method. Several synthesized derivatives demonstrated a significant increase in reaction time in hot plate method, suggesting that these compounds may act through central mechanism, possibly involving GABAergic system. The physicochemical parameters of all synthesized derivatives were determined and found to demonstrate more solubility in organic phases compared to aqueous phases.

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